

GOD Artificial Intelligence (GAI)

Satish Gajawada

IIT Roorkee Alumnus

satish.gajawada.iit@gmail.com

Abstract: A new field titled “GOD Artificial Intelligence” is coined/defined/invented in this article.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; AI; GOD; GOD Artificial Intelligence; GOD AI; GAI

Introduction:

Intelligence - God made.

Artificial Intelligence - Man made.

Artificial Intelligence Papers - Authored by Man.

But what happens when Man and God together publishes an Artificial Intelligence article. For the first time in Artificial Intelligence Research Industry this incident took place and it is called "Lord Rama Artificial Intelligence". I have attached screenshot of a CHAPTER from book titled "Lord Rama Artificial Intelligence" which is available on "Elsevier SSRN Abstract Id – 4599116".

Lord Rama Devotees Algorithm: A New Human-Inspired Metaheuristic Optimization Algorithm

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and

Lord Rama

GOD

Fig. 1 Man and Lord Rama authored Artificial Intelligence article.

Type 1 Intelligence - God made (Intelligence)

Type 2 Intelligence - Man made (Artificial Intelligence)

Type 3 Intelligence - God and Man made (God Artificial Intelligence)

Hence, God Artificial Intelligence is Type 3 Intelligence.

Definition of GOD Artificial Intelligence (GAI): Intelligence is GOD made. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is Man made. When GOD and Man together works on Artificial Intelligence then it comes under “GOD Artificial Intelligence (GAI)”.

Definition of Lord Rama Artificial Intelligence (LRAI): Intelligence is GOD made. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is Man made. When Lord Rama and Man together works on Artificial Intelligence then it comes under “Lord Rama Artificial Intelligence (LRAI)”.

Opportunities in GOD Artificial Intelligence field:

There are many opportunities in GAI field. Some of them are listed below:

- 1) International Institute GAI, Germany
- 2) Indian Institute of GAI, India
- 3) IBM GAI Research Labs, Switzerland
- 4) Google GAI Research Labs, USA
- 5) B.Tech, GAI at IIT Mumbai
- 6) M.Tech, GAI at University of Texas
- 7) PhD, GAI at University of Australia
- 8) PostDoc, GAI at Harvard University
- 9) International Conference on GAI, Singapore
- 10) International Journal on GAI, United Kingdom
- 11) GOD Artificial Intelligence (GAI) – A New Course on Coursera
- 12) Seminar on GAI, Africa
- 13) Book on GAI, Elsevier Publishers

Conclusions: A new field titled “GOD Artificial Intelligence (GAI)” is coined/defined/invented in this article. There are many opportunities in GAI field. Some opportunities in GAI field are listed in this article.